

Mental Health among Adolescents in Single-Parent Families: A Comprehensive Review of Psychosocial Risk and Protective Factors

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The present review aims to synthesize evidence on factors influencing mental health outcomes among adolescents living in single-parent families. Relevant studies were identified through electronic databases, including PubMed, APA PsycArticles, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and JSTOR. A combination of key terms related to family structure, adolescents, single-mother families, single-father families, single-parent families, risk factors, protective factors, personality, social support, psychological problems, and resilience was used. Search terms included “single-parent families” OR “single-mother families” OR “single-father families” AND “adolescent mental health” OR “Big Five personality traits” OR “personality factors” OR “social support” OR “demographic factors” OR “psychological problems” OR “resilience.” Studies showed an increased susceptibility of adolescents in single-parent families to psychological problems because of socio-demographic stress factors and parental distress. Meanwhile, adaptive personality, positive parenting, and strong social support are related to their resilience. However, a very small part of research distinguishes between single-mother and single-father families or uses integrative and mixed-method methodology. The review highlights the importance of the strength-based, culturally sensitive interventions and integrative research approaches for mental health among adolescents living in single-parent families.

Keywords: Adolescents, single-parent families, mental health, risk factors, protective factors

Mental health problems during adolescence are becoming an increasing concern worldwide, as many emotional and behavioral problems begin at an early age and can have lasting effects on a young person's life if left unaddressed (World Health Organization, 2025). Among individuals, about half of all poor mental health conditions diagnosed are noted prior to the age of 14, and nearly three-quarters prior to the age of 24 (Kessler et al., 2005). Barriers such as cultural stigma, lack of awareness, and inadequate mental health services often discourage individuals from seeking help, particularly in India, where only 41 percent of people who were aged between 15 and 24 years expressed their willingness to seek mental health care services (UNICEF, 2021). Several factors contributing to adolescent mental health problems include social withdrawal tendencies, rejection by parents, strong competition among peers in the school setting, over-controlling behaviour by teachers (Steinhausen & Metzke, 2001), emotional abuse, sexual abuse, physical neglect (Wen et al., 2024) and weaker emotional attachment to parents (Oldfield et al., 2016). Although these factors are applicable to adolescents in general, the family environment in

which an adolescent grows up may significantly influence their psychological well-being. The present review examines literature on factors influencing psychological health among adolescents living in single-parent families. Relevant studies were identified through electronic databases, including PubMed, APA PsycArticles, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and JSTOR. Search terms included “single-parent families” OR “single-mother families” OR “single-father families” AND “adolescent mental health” OR “Big Five personality traits” OR “personality factors” OR “social support” OR “demographic factors” OR “psychological problems” OR “resilience.”

Risk Factors for Mental Health among Adolescents from Single-Parent Families

Risk is a higher probability of exposure to a harmful or unpleasant event, whereas risk factors are the recognizable characteristics that predict adverse outcomes according to certain evaluation criteria (Wright et al., 2013). Single-parent families experience greater parenting stress (Berryhill, 2016) and lack of access to income and resources (Ryan & Claessens, 2013). In particular, single-mother families have been reported to face greater financial constraints and reduced support systems (Deepakkumar & Annalakshmi, 2022) which may lead to stress and emotional insecurity among adolescents. Adolescents in single-parent families face peer rejection, discrimination in society and family denial, which lead them to withdraw from family and peer groups and participate in addictive behaviors (Lalmuanawma & Elizabeth, 2021). In India, children brought up in single-parent families show higher risk of academic disruption, food insecurity, and sexual abuse (Uma, 2017) and lower self-esteem (Malik et al., 2022). Interestingly, those living with single fathers exhibited more predisposition to peer-related

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issues (Uma, 2017) while those raised by single mothers reported greater early life stress and rumination (Daryanani et al., 2016). Adolescents in single-parent families have greater emotional and behavioral difficulties (Maurya et al., 2015), reduced emotional stability (Lahiri & Verma, 2023), lower resilience (Devi & Rani, 2023), and poor academic performance (Kunjachan et al., 2021). Divorce of parents leads to mental health problems (Karhina et al., 2023), such as anxiety, depression, reduced subjective wellness, lower self-esteem, and school-related problems (Storksen et al., 2015), with recent evidence indicating increased stress (Tran et al., 2023), social fear, and suicidal ideation among affected adolescents (Obeid et al., 2021). The risk for depressive symptoms is higher among adolescents living with single parents (Ang et al., 2019; Magklara et al., 2015), where maternal psychological distress contributes to higher anxiety and depression levels among adolescents (Leung et al., 2023). Prolonged absence of a parent further increases the risk of depressive symptoms (Cen et al., 2025), and adolescents fail to get the emotional support they require at the moment of stress (Zhao, 2023).

Protective Factors for Mental Health among Adolescents from Single-Parent Families

Protective factors determine the response of an individual to environmental risks, and they serve in minimizing or altering the risk of adverse results (Rutter, 1985). Lifestyle-related factors like physical exercise and sufficient sleep improve the adaptive capacity of adolescents, with physical exercise showing a stronger association with resilience among males (Marquez et al., 2023). Adolescents in single-parent families have responsible health practices and goal-oriented attitudes like vigorous exercise and healthy food habits (DeGuzman et al., 2023). Individuals with higher educational goals have lower engagement in risky activities and have reduced sexual risk-taking (Roberts et al., 2011). Gratitude, seeking social support, and effective stress management practices promote emotional well-being among adolescents from single-parent families (DeGuzman et al., 2023). Social maturity in boys and emotional maturity in girls are positively related to adjustment (Upreti, 2018). Adolescents with single parents who can control their emotions and participate in positive interpersonal relationships report higher well-being (Sia & Aneesh, 2024). Optimism, determination, spiritual belief, emotional openness, self-assurance (Greeff & Ritman, 2005), and family unity, solidarity, and affirming practices promote resilience among individuals in single-parent families (Hsieh & Leung, 2009). A sense of acceptance, protection, involvement, and care fosters optimism and positive mental health (Sahu, 2016), and satisfaction in relationships with others reduces emotional distress (Kenny et al., 2013). Emotional attachment or feeling of intimacy is most often discussed by single-parent families as their utmost source of strength (Ford-Gilboe, 2000). Adolescents in single-parent families who were in 8th and 9th grades, female, and studied in government school showed better mental health (Mohan & Priya, 2020).

Demographic Factors and Adolescent Mental Health

Socio-demographic factors like gender, socioeconomic status, school environment, parental education, and household income have been cited as contributing factors to behavioral problems among adolescents (Prasanth & Annalakshmi, 2020). Age is a factor that correlates with the mental health of adolescents, with younger

individuals reporting poorer mental health than their older peers (Najmi et al., 2019). In single-parent families, adolescents around 15 years of age showed lower resilience and had more difficulty in controlling their emotions (Sia & Aneesh, 2024) while those aged 16-19 had more negative life experiences, placing them at higher risk for mental health problems (Karhina et al., 2023). Apart from age, adolescents of both genders are vulnerable to dysfunctional family environments, emotion-oriented coping, and poor performance in schools (Martyn et al., 2014) with girls demonstrating a higher potential of developing mental health problems (Tiwari & Jaiswal, 2020). Girls from single-father families are more vulnerable to psychological problems (Megha & Annalakshmi, 2026). Female students who had to live without a family showed more mental disturbances, probably due to lower emotional support (Chandrashekarappa et al., 2016). The prevalence of emotional problems was higher in girls living with single parents (Matti & Itagi, 2021) and they are more likely to internalize the problems (Dray et al., 2016). Conversely, boys are prone to externalizing behaviors (Dray et al., 2016) and have a higher risk for mental health (Annalakshmi et al., 2024).

The place of residence, parental education, and employment status also contribute to adolescent mental health. The incidence of mental health problems is found to be higher among urban adolescents who belong to single-parent families than among their rural counterparts (Matti & Itagi, 2021). The stress-inducing nature of urban settings, where people are likely to experience the need to compete with each other academically and socially, follow a busy schedule, and lose a sense of community, is likely to worsen stress and reduce the ability to access helpful networks. Conversely, rural adolescents living in single-parent families face challenges in emotional development, restricted social contacts, and poor family relationships (Devi, 2007). Education and occupation of parents have been observed to be associated with the adolescent's mental health. Children with externalizing behaviors were also found to be more likely to belong to households that had unmarried single parents with poor education levels and belonged to rental or subsidized housing facilities. Conversely, children with internalizing problems tended to be brought up in families that had working parents (Alavi et al., 2017). Overall, demographic factors seem to be active and dynamic factors influencing adolescents' well-being.

Big Five Personality and Adolescent Mental Health

Internal factors, particularly Big Five factors, influence the level of involvement and participation of the adolescents in academic and social aspects (Rashedi & Abolmaali, 2014). Reduced extraversion and conscientiousness, combined with increased neuroticism, negatively contribute to depressive symptoms (Hakulinen et al., 2015). Extraversion has also been attributed to reduced anxiety and greater positive mental health (Patwari & Vajpayee, 2023). Emotionally stable adolescents are happier and less depressed and anxious (Diaconu-Gherasim & Mardari, 2022), and together with extraversion, it predicts better emotion regulation and emotional self-efficacy, leading to psychological resilience (Domenech et al., 2024). Individuals with agreeableness and conscientiousness characteristics are less prone to displaying signs of social problems and anhedonia (Kang et al., 2023), anxiety (Patwari & Vajpayee,

2023), and perceived loneliness (Buecker et al., 2020), and have higher psychological resilience (Prakash & Bindhu, 2021). Sociability, cooperativeness, and readiness for new experiences are related to a greater sense of self-worth (Davey et al., 2003).

Comparative research has established that the adolescents in single-parent families, and specifically those raised by single mothers, score lower in extraversion, agreeableness, and openness to experience than those brought up with two parents (Shah et al., 2017). The authoritative style was the most frequently seen approach in both single-parent and two-parent families (Ghani et al., 2014) and adolescents raised in such environments are more open, conscientious, extraverted, and agreeable, and less neurotic (Tehrani et al., 2024). Openness is one of the traits that has demonstrated the most robust correlation with health literacy, with a strong effect in single-parent and two-parent family contexts (Mai et al., 2022). Adolescents living in single-mother families are resilient in emotionally distressing scenarios, which makes it possible to infer that adaptive coping strategies develop within such environments. Interestingly, adolescents in single-parent families tend to demonstrate a higher level of ego strength, conscientiousness, perseverance, and responsibility than those in two-parent families (Moldovan, 2016). These characteristics could be the adaptive responses to the heightened number of familial responsibilities and social demands. Children brought up in single-parent families tend to have higher responsibility and agreeableness (Lahiri & Verma, 2023) which may be shaped by social expectations and family dynamics they face, promoting maturity in early life and cooperative behavior among them. Research findings indicate that single-parent adolescents do not always have poor emotional well-being (Jagdeesh et al., 2018) and factors like social support may influence their mental health.

Social Support and Adolescent Mental Health

Social support includes emotional comfort, practical assistance, and exchange of useful information, as well as a sense of belonging in the social networks. They not only enhance individual resilience but also represent some of the main functions of a family system (Ozbay et al., 2007). During adolescence, individuals are inclined to find support from those people who are emotionally stable, trustworthy, friendly, and experienced, with emotional support prioritized when perfectly aligned with their needs and situations (Camara et al., 2017). Healthy connections with parents and friends significantly influence the mental well-being of adolescents (Kenny et al., 2013). Social support by family, friends, and teachers was observed as an important predictor of life satisfaction among adolescents who were raised by a single parent (Dikilitaş et al., 2023). Support from fathers is linked to a higher sense of meaning in life and enhanced subjective well-being, while support from teachers also positively influences the meaning of life for adolescents (Jakobsen et al., 2022). Adolescents who are connected with their communities and those who claim to have a supportive female figure possess greater levels of hope (Cheng et al., 2014).

Family support affects depression, anxiety, and stress, along with overall well-being, with self-esteem acting as a mediator in these relationships, while peer support demonstrates a beneficial direct link to well-being (Gardner & Webb, 2019). Family support reduces depression symptoms and delinquency, whereas peer support had a reduced result on depression but varied effects on delinquency (Licitra-Kleckler & Waas, 1993). Young individuals who had

difficulties at home had low self-esteem in comparison with those in more positive settings (Valsala et al., 2018). Adolescents from single-parent families who have experienced bullying have lower life satisfaction, yet perceived family support acted as a partial buffer of the adverse outcomes (Erdogan et al., 2023). Family support aids in building resilience in adolescents coming from single-parent families (Anggraini et al., 2022). The support received by the parents also influences the well-being of their children. Social support is vital in defining and determining the general well-being of single mothers (Muarifah et al., 2024) which leads to emotional stability and life satisfaction among their children. Single mothers are likely to spend their time in practical, task-focused activities, whereas single fathers are bound to spend their time in leisure and recreation with their children (Asmussen & Larson, 1991). Such different patterns of relationships might help to create self-reliance and flexibility, especially in cases of adolescents who are brought up by single parents (Hsieh & Shek, 2008). For adolescents growing up in single-mother families, family is not limited to the biological bonds and traditional family but a feeling of emotional attachments and experiences (Jain, 2020). The emotional connection that adolescents have with their mother has been associated with a high resilience rate and reduced reliance on emotion-focused coping strategies (Guo, 2019). Social support and family functioning in divorced families had a distinct contribution towards all the aspects of adolescent adaptation (Hsieh & Leung, 2009).

Research Gaps in Existing Literature and Future Directions

India is experiencing a tremendous change in family setups, increasing cases of divorce, changing social values, and rising cases of parental loss. The focus on the well-being of adolescents has increased over the past years, but there are still considerable gaps, especially in the field of resilience of adolescents in families with single parents in India. A major flaw in the existing literature is the fact that single-parent families have been treated as a homogeneous group, rarely distinguishing between single-mother and single-father families. Closely connected with this is the little research done on parent-adolescent gender matching. Integrative models that combine socio-demographic factors, personality characteristics, social support, psychological problems, and resilience are scarce, and qualitative insights into adolescents' lived experiences in single-mother and single-father families remain underexplored. Mixed-method designs, especially sequential explanatory designs, may provide a deeper understanding of the nature of interaction between risk and protective factors in diverse family structures.

Conclusion

This review examined the risk and protective factors influencing mental health among adolescents in single-parent families. Although research highlights increased vulnerability to emotional, behavioral, and academic difficulties, evidence also shows significant resilience among adolescents in single-parent families shaped by personality traits, social support, parenting styles, and socio-demographic factors. Mental health outcomes are not determined by family structure alone but by the interaction of internal strengths and external resources. A strength-based and integrative approach is essential to understand adolescents' adaptive capacities. Future research should adopt comprehensive and mixed-method designs to better capture resilience processes and inform

culturally sensitive interventions that promote adolescent well-being.

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